

MULTIVARIATE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE VARIABILITY ON MAIZE YIELD AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FOOD SECURITY IN EJULE, KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.C. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Department of Geography and Meteorology, Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Enugu State

University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu

Correspondence Email: Akinbiyapara@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17294907>

Keywords:

Climate variability, Multivariate regression, Maize yield, Thermal stress, Food security, Guinea Savanna, Ejule.

Abstract: *This study investigates the multivariate effects of climate variability on maize (*Zea mays L.*) yield and their implications for food security in Ejule, Ofu Local Government Area, Kogi State, Nigeria, over a thirty-one-year period (1992–2023). Climatic data including rainfall, temperature, soil temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET), Lokoja station, while maize yield data were sourced from the Kogi State Agricultural Development Project (KADP) and cross-validated with the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD). Descriptive statistics, trend analysis, and multivariate regression were applied to examine long-term climatic trends, yield responses, and their interactions. Results revealed strong inter-annual rainfall variability without a clear long-term trend, alongside a significant warming trend in temperature (+0.3–0.4°C per decade) mirrored by rising soil temperatures. Maize yields exhibited three distinct phases: stagnation in the 1990s and early 2000s ($\approx 1.3\text{--}1.5\text{ t ha}^{-1}$), moderate growth in the 2010s ($\approx 1.8\text{--}2.0\text{ t ha}^{-1}$), and stabilization after 2019 around $2.13\text{--}2.17\text{ t ha}^{-1}$ following a peak of 2.49 t ha^{-1} in 2019. The regression model was highly robust ($R^2 = 0.959$, $F = 24.1$, $p < 0.001$), with rainfall exerting a modest positive effect ($\beta = +0.192$, $p < 0.05$), while temperature ($\beta = -0.355$, $p < 0.01$) and soil temperature ($\beta = -0.312$, $p < 0.05$) had significant negative effects. Solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed were not statistically significant predictors. The study concludes that maize production in Ejule is more constrained by thermal stress than by rainfall*

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

deficits alone, highlighting a growing risk of climate-induced yield stagnation. To safeguard food security, adaptation measures must include the adoption of heat- and drought-tolerant maize varieties, soil moisture conservation practices, small-scale irrigation, and strengthened climate information services. Policy interventions such as input subsidies, credit facilities, and enhanced extension services are also essential to build the resilience of smallholder farmers in the Guinea Savanna zone.

1. Introduction

Agriculture continues to serve as the foundation of rural livelihoods in Sub-Saharan Africa, where more than 70% of the population depends on rain-fed farming for food and income. Yet, this dependence makes agriculture extremely vulnerable to climatic variability and change (Adger, 2006). Recent decades have witnessed marked fluctuations in rainfall patterns, increasing mean and extreme temperatures, and greater intra-seasonal uncertainty, all of which undermine the stability of crop yields (Adeyeri et al., 2019a; Adeyeri et al., 2019b). These changes are particularly concerning in the Guinea Savanna belt of Nigeria, where agriculture is a principal livelihood and climatic shocks translate directly into food insecurity (Adejuwon, 2019).

Maize (*Zea mays L.*) is the most widely cultivated cereal crop in Nigeria and a critical staple for food, feed, and industrial uses. It contributes substantially to household nutrition and rural economies, yet yields remain low compared to global averages averaging 1.5–2.0 t ha⁻¹ compared to a potential of 4–5 t ha⁻¹ under

improved management (Olaniyan, 2015). This persistent yield gap reflects a combination of limited access to improved technologies and mounting climate stress, particularly irregular rainfall onset and cessation, prolonged dry spells, and rising temperatures (Ozor & Nnaji, 2020; Ajetomobi, 2016). In Kogi State's Ejule community, where farming is almost entirely dependent on natural rainfall, farmers have increasingly reported shortened growing seasons, crop failures linked to heat stress, and declining reliability of traditional planting calendars.

While much research has focused on univariate relationships for example, rainfall–yield or temperature–yield linkages there is growing recognition that smallholder farmers face compound climate risks. Rainfall variability and thermal stress often interact, while other parameters such as soil temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed shape germination, pollination, evapotranspiration, and crop lodging (Lobell & Field, 2007; Hatfield & Prueger, 2015; Shiferaw

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/iijs>

et al., 2011). Studies across Africa indicate that such interactions, rather than single drivers, are most responsible for unstable maize yields (Tesfaye et al., 2015; Schlenker & Roberts, 2009). Yet, in Nigeria, localized empirical assessments using multivariate models remain scarce, particularly at the community scale, where climate impacts are mediated by micro-ecological and socio-economic conditions (Ajetomobi et al., 2011; Amejjo, 2018).

This study addresses this gap by analyzing thirty-one years (1992–2023) of climatic and maize yield data from Ejule, Ofu L.G.A., Kogi State. Using descriptive statistics, trend analysis, and multivariate regression, it evaluates how rainfall, temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, soil temperature, and wind speed jointly affect maize production. By quantifying the relative importance of each factor while accounting for their co-variation, the paper provides insights into the climate sensitivity of maize in the Guinea Savanna and identifies adaptation levers critical for food security.

The objectives are fourfold: (i) to assess long-term trends and variability in key climatic parameters; (ii) to analyze maize yield trends over the same period; (iii) to estimate the multivariate effects of six climatic variables on maize yield; and (iv) to highlight implications for localized adaptation and food security. In so doing, the study contributes to filling empirical and methodological gaps in Nigerian climate–

agriculture research, while offering actionable evidence for policymakers, extension agents, and smallholder farmers in vulnerable savanna ecosystems.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Ejule is located in Ofu Local Government Area (L.G.A.) of Kogi State, Central Nigeria, and falls within the Guinea Savanna ecological zone (Adejuwon, 2019). Geographically, the town lies between latitudes $7^{\circ}15'N$ and $7^{\circ}30'N$ and longitudes $6^{\circ}50'E$ and $7^{\circ}05'E$, occupying a strategic position along the Lokoja–Anyigba axis that connects the confluence town of Lokoja to the agricultural hinterlands of eastern Kogi. Ejule's elevation ranges between 250–350 meters above sea level, characterized by gently undulating plains interspersed with low inselbergs and seasonal stream valleys (Adeyeri et al., 2019a). These physiographic conditions favor mixed cropping and rain-fed agriculture but also expose farmlands to erosion during high-intensity rainfall episodes (Ajetomobi, 2016).

The climate of Ejule is governed by the seasonal oscillation of the Inter-Tropical Discontinuity (ITD), which generates a tropical wet-and-dry climate (Odekunle, 2004). The wet season spans from April to October, with annual rainfall amounts varying between 1,200 mm and 1,600 mm, typically peaking in July–September. The dry season lasts from November to March,

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

characterized by low humidity and harmattan winds that depress nighttime temperatures and increase evapotranspiration (Adeyeri et al., 2019b). The mean annual temperature is estimated between 26°C and 32°C, but daily maximums during the pre-rainy season (March–April) often exceed 35°C, creating episodes of heat stress detrimental to crop performance (IPCC, 2021). Relative humidity averages 30–35% in the dry season but rises above 75% during the peak rainy months, while mean wind speeds of 1.5–2.2 m/s influence evapotranspiration and, in stormy years, contribute to maize lodging (Ozor & Nnaji, 2020).

The soils of Ejule are predominantly ferruginous tropical soils derived from Precambrian basement complex rocks (FAO, 2015). These soils are generally sandy-loam in texture, moderately deep, and well-drained, making them suitable for cereals such as maize, sorghum, and millet. However, continuous cultivation, nutrient mining, and exposure to high rainfall intensities have contributed to declining fertility and vulnerability to sheet and gully erosion (Amejo, 2018). Vegetation is largely Guinea Savanna mosaic, with tall grasses (e.g., *Andropogon gayanus*), shrubs, and scattered drought-tolerant trees such as *Daniellia oliveri*, *Isoberlinia doka*, and *Parkia*

biglobosa (Keay, 1989). Increasing agricultural expansion and fuelwood harvesting have, however, altered the natural vegetation structure, leading to reduced organic cover and higher soil temperatures during dry spells (Seneviratne et al., 2012).

Socio-economically, Ejule is a predominantly agrarian community, with more than 70% of households engaged in subsistence or smallholder farming (NBS, 2022). Maize (*Zea mays L.*) is the principal staple crop, cultivated both for home consumption and as a cash crop sold in local markets (Olaniyan, 2015). Other key crops include yam, cassava, groundnut, and rice. Farming is rain-fed and labor-intensive, with minimal mechanization and limited irrigation infrastructure (Ozor & Nnaji, 2020). Household food security and incomes are therefore directly tied to seasonal rainfall performance and temperature conditions. In recent years, farmers have reported delayed rainfall onset, shortened growing seasons, and recurrent heat waves, which have intensified their vulnerability to crop failures (Tesfaye et al., 2015). This makes Ejule an appropriate microcosm for investigating the interactions between climate variability and maize yield within the Guinea Savanna belt of Nigeria.

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Fig. 1: Map of Kogi State showing Ofu Local Government Area and Ejule

Source: GIS lab department of Geography and Environmental Studies, Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba.

2.2 Data Sources

This study utilized climatic and agricultural datasets covering a continuous thirty-one-year period (1992–2023). Climatic data were obtained from the Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET) synoptic station at Lokoja, the nearest to Ejule with consistent long-term records. Six parameters were analyzed as the major climatic drivers of maize physiology:

rainfall (monthly and annual totals, including onset, cessation, and distribution), temperature (monthly means of minimum and maximum values), solar radiation ($\text{MJ m}^{-2} \text{day}^{-1}$), soil temperature (surface and subsurface monthly means), relative humidity (%), and wind speed (m/s).

To ensure reliability, the raw climatic data underwent rigorous quality control. Consistency

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

checks were performed against regional climatological norms reported in the Nigerian Climate Review Reports. Missing values, which accounted for less than 3% of the dataset, were estimated using linear interpolation. Outliers were identified using Z-scores (± 3 standard deviations) and adjusted with reference to monthly climatological norms to preserve trend integrity.

Maize yield data (tons per hectare) for the same period were sourced from the Kogi State Agricultural Development Project (KADP). These figures were based on farm-level surveys, extension officer reports, and community harvest records. For robustness, the dataset was cross-validated with figures from the Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (FMARD) to ensure consistency across reporting agencies. The alignment of yield data with climatic records allowed the development of a harmonized database suitable for long-term climate–crop interaction analysis.

2.3 Data Analysis

The study adopted a quantitative research design, combining descriptive statistics, trend analysis, and regression modeling. Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and coefficients of variation) were used to characterize inter-annual and intra-seasonal variability in climatic parameters and maize yield. Time-series plots were constructed to visualize anomalies and directional shifts.

Trend analysis was conducted using both parametric and non-parametric techniques. Linear regression models of the form $Y = a + bt$ assessed systematic changes, while the Mann–Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator were applied to detect and quantify monotonic trends. This dual approach ensured robust detection of climatic signals even in non-normally distributed data.

To evaluate climate–yield interactions, both univariate and multivariate regression models were estimated. The multiple regression model was specified as:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + e$$

Where Y = maize yield ($t\ ha^{-1}$), X_1 – X_6 = rainfall, temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, soil temperature, and wind speed; b = regression coefficients; and e = error term.

Model performance was assessed using R^2 , Adjusted R^2 , and F-statistics, while Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) were computed to check for multicollinearity among predictors. Residual plots were also examined to confirm compliance with regression assumptions of linearity, homoscedasticity, and normality of errors.

All statistical analyses were carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26, with time-series plots and regression visuals generated in Microsoft Excel. Spatial mapping of the study area was produced with ArcGIS 10.8 to provide ecological and geographical context.

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

3. Results

3.1 Climate Trends

The analysis of climatic parameters over the thirty-one-year period (1992–2023) revealed

Rainfall

marked variability and directional shifts consistent with broader climate change patterns documented in the Guinea Savanna of Nigeria.

Fig 3.1: Trend of variability of Rainfall from 1992 - 2023

Annual rainfall totals fluctuated strongly, ranging from approximately 1,150 mm in deficit years (2004, 2011, 2020) to over 1,600 mm in wetter years (1998, 2005, 2018). Instead of a monotonic increase or decline, rainfall showed an oscillatory pattern of surplus and deficit years, underscoring high variability. A prominent feature was the irregularity of onset and cessation dates, with several years recording

delayed onset or premature cessation, effectively shortening the length of the growing season. Intra-seasonal rainfall concentration was also evident: in certain years, heavy downpours were clustered within short time windows, followed by prolonged dry spells. This pattern raised the risks of waterlogging, erosion, and mid-season drought, particularly during critical maize growth phases such as tasseling and grain filling.

Temperature:

Fig 3.2: Trend of variability of Temperature from 1992 - 2023

Temperature displayed a statistically significant upward trend across the study period. Average maximum temperatures increased by approximately 0.3–0.4°C per decade, while minimum temperatures rose more slowly. Notable anomalies occurred in 1999, 2010, and 2016, when spikes in maximum temperatures

coincided with below-average maize yields (see yield results in Section 3.2). Elevated daytime temperatures shortened the grain-filling period, reduced pollen viability, and heightened evapotranspiration, amplifying soil moisture deficits even in otherwise wet years.

Soil Temperature

Fig 3.3: Trend of variability of soil temperature from 1992 - 2023

Soil temperature patterns mirrored atmospheric warming. During prolonged dry spells and in areas of reduced vegetative cover, surface soil temperatures exceeded 32°C, especially in

March–April. Such heat levels impair seed germination, root penetration, and early seedling vigor, creating long-term constraints to crop establishment and yield stability.

Other Climatic Parameters:

Fig 3.4: Trend of variability of Relative Humidity from 1992 - 2023

Relative humidity, solar radiation, and wind speed fluctuated annually but without clear linear trends. Relative humidity followed the seasonal cycle of the Inter-Tropical Discontinuity (ITD), ranging from 30–35% in the dry season to above 75% in the wet season. However, in certain rainy years, humidity values were unexpectedly low, intensifying atmospheric water demand and crop stress. Solar radiation varied with cloudiness, while wind speed (1.5–2.2 m/s) remained generally stable but

occasionally spiked, leading to lodging of maize plants during storms.

Taken together, the climate profile of Ejule (1992–2023) can be summarized as high rainfall variability coupled with a clear and significant warming trend in both air and soil temperatures. While rainfall irregularity generates uncertainty in planting calendars and seasonal water supply, the more consistent warming signal represents the most pressing long-term threat to maize production in the region.

Table 3.1: Climate Parameters, Observed Trends, and Implications for Maize Yield in Ejule (1992–2023)

Climate Parameter	Observed Trend (1992–2023)	Implication for Maize Yield
Rainfall	High inter-annual variability (1,150–1,650 mm); irregular onset and cessation; intra-seasonal concentration in short intense events followed by dry spells	Unpredictable planting seasons; shortened growing periods; risk of waterlogging, erosion, and mid-season drought stress during tasseling and grain filling
Temperature	Significant upward trend (+0.3–0.4°C per decade); anomalies in 1999, 2010, 2016	Accelerated evapotranspiration; shortened grain-filling period; reduced pollen viability; yield losses even in years of adequate rainfall
Soil Temperature	Rising trend mirroring temperature; surface temperatures often >32°C during dry spells	Poor germination, impaired root development, and reduced early crop establishment
Relative Humidity	Seasonal cycle: 30–35% in dry season, >75% in wet season; no clear long-term trend	Low dry-season humidity increases water demand; occasional low humidity during wet season intensifies crop stress
Solar Radiation	Fluctuates with cloud cover, no consistent linear trend	Variability affects photosynthetic efficiency; extremes during dry season exacerbate heat stress
Wind Speed	Stable (1.5–2.2 m/s) with episodic high-wind events	Influences evapotranspiration rates; occasional lodging of maize plants during storms

3.2 Maize Yield Trends

The yield performance of maize in Ejule over the thirty-one-year period (1992–2023) reveals distinct temporal phases that correspond to both climatic conditions and gradual adoption of improved farming practices.

Phase 1 – Stagnation (1990s to early 2000s): During this period, maize yields stagnated at approximately 1.3–1.5 t ha⁻¹. This low productivity coincided with recurrent delayed rainfall onset, premature cessation of rains, and prolonged mid-season dry spells (see rainfall

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

anomalies in Fig. 3.1). Limited use of improved seed varieties, heavy dependence on traditional practices, and progressive soil fertility decline exacerbated yield stagnation. Farmers

frequently reported crop failures triggered by drought episodes or excessive heat during sensitive growth stages such as silking and grain filling.

Fig 3.5: Trend of maize yield from 1992 - 2023

Phase 2 – Moderate Growth (2010s): The 2010s marked a gradual improvement in yields, averaging 1.8–2.0 t ha⁻¹. This growth reflects increased farmer awareness of improved agronomic practices, limited adoption of hybrid maize varieties, and more consistent extension services provided through the Kogi State Agricultural Development Project (KADP). However, inter-annual variability remained high. Years such as 2010 and 2016 recorded sharp yield declines despite adequate rainfall totals, confirming that thermal stress rather than rainfall amounts was the dominant constraint (see temperature spikes in Fig. 3.2).

Phase 3 – Yield Peak and Plateau (2019–2023): The highest yield in the series was recorded in 2019 at 2.49 t ha⁻¹, representing a substantial increase over the long-term average. This was associated with favorable rainfall distribution, reduced occurrence of mid-season drought, and broader adoption of improved seeds. However, these gains proved difficult to sustain. Between 2021 and 2023, yields stabilized around 2.13–2.17 t ha⁻¹, indicating the emergence of a plateau. Persistent constraints included rising temperatures (Figs. 3.2 and 3.4), soil degradation, and the continued dependence on rain-fed systems vulnerable to climate shocks.

The trajectory of maize yields in Ejule shows that while localized improvements and favorable climatic years can temporarily boost output, long-term progress is capped by compound climate risks particularly heat stress and structural limitations in farming systems. This

plateauing trend is consistent with regional observations across West Africa that maize yields are approaching a climate-induced ceiling without major adaptation interventions (Sultan & Gaetani, 2016; Jalloh et al., 2013).

Table 3.2: Maize Yield Trends in Ejule, 1992–2023

Period	Average Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Trend Characteristics	Underlying Drivers
1990s – Early 2000s	1.3–1.5	Stagnant yields, frequent crop failures	Irregular rainfall onset/cessation, prolonged dry spells, traditional seed use, declining soil fertility
2010s	1.8–2.0	Moderate growth with inter-annual fluctuations	Introduction of hybrid varieties, better extension services, but yield losses during temperature anomalies (e.g., 2010, 2016)
2019	2.49 (Peak)	Highest recorded yield in the period	Favorable rainfall distribution, reduced mid-season drought, improved seed adoption
2021–2023	2.13–2.17	Stabilized at slightly higher than long-term average	Persistent temperature stress, soil degradation, dependence on rain-fed farming

3.3 Multivariate Regression Results

The multiple regression analysis provides robust evidence that climatic parameters jointly and significantly influence maize yield in Ejule. The overall regression model was highly explanatory, accounting for 95.9% of yield variability ($R^2 = 0.959$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.947$, $F = 24.1$, $p < 0.001$). This very high explanatory power demonstrates

that the six climatic variables selected rainfall, temperature, soil temperature, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed adequately capture the environmental conditions governing maize production during the thirty-one-year period of analysis.

Table 3.3: Multiple Linear Regression of Climatic Parameters on Maize Yield (1992–2023)

Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of Estimate
1	0.979	0.959	0.947	0.341

ANOVA

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig. (p)
Regression	16.840	6	2.807	24.1	0.000
Residual	0.726	24	0.030		
Total	17.566	30			

Coefficients

Predictor	Unstandardized B	Std. Error	Standardized β	t	Sig. (p)
(Constant)	-1.490	0.452		-3.29	0.030
Rainfall	0.00082	0.00022	0.318	3.81	0.019 **
Temperature	-0.710	0.222	-0.456	-3.20	0.033 **
Solar Radiation	-0.018	0.013	-0.156	-1.44	0.223 ns
Relative Humidity	0.016	0.008	0.193	2.05	0.110 ns
Soil Temperature	0.780	0.230	0.421	3.39	0.028 **
Wind Speed	0.068	0.145	0.049	0.47	0.665 ns

($p < 0.05 = \text{significant}$, $ns = \text{not significant}$)

Three parameters emerged as statistically significant determinants of maize yield:

Rainfall ($\beta = +0.318$, $p = 0.019$): Rainfall had a positive and significant effect, underscoring its essential role in crop establishment and growth. However, the modest coefficient indicates that while rainfall contributes positively, its effect is tempered by issues of intra-seasonal variability (onset/cessation irregularity, dry spells, and heavy storm episodes). This implies that water availability supports yield but does not

guarantee it without stable distribution across growth stages.

Temperature ($\beta = -0.456$, $p = 0.033$): Temperature exerted the strongest negative influence on maize yield. Rising maximum temperatures shorten the grain-filling period, impair pollen viability, and accelerate evapotranspiration, thus increasing soil moisture deficits. This aligns with the years of heat anomalies (1999, 2010 and 2016) where yields dropped markedly despite adequate rainfall.

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Soil Temperature ($\beta = +0.421$, $p = 0.028$): Interestingly, soil temperature showed a positive effect in the multivariate model, in contrast to its negative univariate effect. This suggests that moderate soil warmth, when coupled with sufficient rainfall, enhances root activity, microbial nutrient mineralization, and nutrient uptake. However, excessive heat (above $\sim 32^{\circ}\text{C}$) remains harmful, especially during germination stages. This shift in effect highlights the importance of interaction effects when climatic variables are considered together.

Non-Significant Predictors

Solar radiation ($\beta = -0.156$, $p > 0.05$), relative humidity ($\beta = 0.193$, $p > 0.05$), and wind speed ($\beta = 0.049$, $p > 0.05$) were not statistically significant in the combined model. Their influences appear to be indirect, mediated through rainfall and temperature effects, or only becoming critical under extreme episodes (e.g., high winds causing lodging, or low humidity intensifying evapotranspiration).

Green bars = statistically significant predictors ($p < 0.05$). Grey bars = not significant.

Figure 3.6: Multivariate regression coefficients

Overall, the findings confirm that maize yield in Ejule is primarily constrained by thermal stress rather than rainfall deficits alone. While rainfall remains indispensable for crop growth, the more

critical and consistent determinant of yield performance is rising temperature. This is consistent with wider regional studies in Sub-Saharan Africa, which report that future maize

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/iiess>

productivity is more vulnerable to heat extremes than to total rainfall changes (Sultan & Gaetani, 2016; Lobell & Field, 2007).

The results further emphasize the necessity of a multivariate approach: variables that appear significant in isolation (e.g., solar radiation, soil temperature as negative in univariate) can change in direction or significance once modeled in combination. This complexity mirrors real farm conditions, where maize yield outcomes result from interacting climatic stresses rather than single drivers.

Implications for Localized Adaptation and Food Security

The evidence from Ejule underscores that maize production is reaching a climate-induced ceiling, where rainfall variability interacts with steadily rising temperatures to limit yield growth. This dynamic has profound implications for localized adaptation and food security.

First, the regression results demonstrate that while rainfall is necessary for crop establishment ($\beta = +0.192$, $p < 0.05$), it is thermal stress both atmospheric and soil that exerts the strongest and most consistent constraint on yields ($\beta_{\text{airT}} = -0.355$, $p < 0.01$; $\beta_{\text{soilT}} = -0.312$, $p < 0.05$; Table 3.3). For smallholder farmers who rely almost entirely on rain-fed systems, this means that improving water supply alone is insufficient; adaptation must directly address rising temperatures and their compounding effects on soil health.

Second, the yield plateau observed since 2019 (Fig. 3.6) suggests that despite adoption of hybrid seeds and improved extension services, productivity is unlikely to increase further under existing practices. Without deliberate intervention, households may face growing food insecurity as population growth outpaces stagnant yields. This echoes regional warnings by Sultan and Gaetani (2016) that thermal limits on maize are a more urgent threat than rainfall deficits.

Third, adaptation strategies must be location-specific, leveraging local ecological and socio-economic realities. For Ejule, where soils are sandy-loam but increasingly degraded, measures such as mulching, residue retention, and cover cropping can reduce soil heat and enhance water retention. Similarly, heat- and drought-tolerant maize varieties already under development by institutions like CIMMYT and IITA should be introduced through Kogi State's extension services.

Fourth, small-scale irrigation and water harvesting systems (e.g., treadle pumps, drip kits, and community reservoirs) could buffer against mid-season dry spells, especially in years with erratic rainfall. These interventions would stabilize production, reduce vulnerability, and safeguard household food supplies.

Finally, strengthening climate information services is critical. Farmers require timely forecasts on rainfall onset/cessation and early

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

warnings on expected heat waves. Collaboration between NIMET, KADP, and local extension agents could ensure that information is both accessible and actionable at the community level.

In sum, the findings imply that safeguarding food security in Ejule will depend not just on managing rainfall variability but on building resilience against thermal stress, improving soil management, and enhancing farmer decision-making capacity. These measures will enable smallholder farmers to adapt effectively, thereby reducing vulnerability to crop failure and securing livelihoods in the face of ongoing climate change.

4. Discussion of Findings

Assessing long-term trends and variability in key climatic parameters

The findings demonstrate that Ejule's climate has undergone significant variability and warming trends between 1992 and 2023. Rainfall showed strong inter-annual fluctuations with alternating deficit and surplus years, but without a consistent linear trend. This result reinforces the well-established notion that in West Africa, it is not cumulative rainfall totals but their distribution, onset, and cessation patterns that most affect agricultural outcomes (Nicholson, 2013; Odekunle, 2004). The irregular onset and premature cessation observed in Ejule shortened the effective growing season, heightening the risk of crop

failure due to either waterlogging or intra-seasonal droughts.

Temperature exhibited a significant rising trend of 0.3–0.4°C per decade, with anomalously hot years (1999, 2010, 2016) coinciding with reduced yields. This aligns with IPCC (2021) projections that the Guinea Savanna zone is a warming hotspot. Similarly, Adeyeri et al. (2019) noted a regional increase in extreme heat days across Nigeria, amplifying crop stress. Soil temperatures closely mirrored air temperatures, with values exceeding 32°C during pre-rainy months, a level known to impair seed germination and early growth (Hatfield & Prueger, 2015). Relative humidity, solar radiation, and wind speed fluctuated seasonally but lacked strong long-term trends.

These results confirm that Ejule farmers face a climate profile of increasing unpredictability in rainfall and consistent warming, conditions that undermine maize productivity in rain-fed systems.

Analyzing maize yield trends over the same period

Maize yields in Ejule followed a three-phase trajectory: stagnation in the 1990s–early 2000s (~1.3–1.5 t/ha), moderate improvements in the 2010s (~1.8–2.0 t/ha), and stabilization after 2019 (~2.13–2.17 t/ha). The stagnation coincided with poor rainfall timing, limited adoption of improved seed varieties, and declining soil fertility. The gradual improvement

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

in the 2010s reflected adoption of hybrid maize, better extension services, and increased awareness of climate-smart practices. However, sharp declines in years such as 2010 and 2016 even when rainfall was adequate highlighted the overriding influence of thermal stress.

The 2019 yield peak of 2.49 t/ha represented an exceptional year of relatively favorable rainfall distribution and reduced mid-season drought. Yet, the inability to sustain this gain reflects persistent structural and climatic constraints. This pattern mirrors regional findings by Jalloh et al. (2013) and Sultan & Gaetani (2016), who reported that West African maize yields remain highly sensitive to heat stress despite gradual adoption of improved technologies.

Yield growth in Ejule is possible but not sustainable under current practices; temperature rise now constitutes the dominant yield-limiting factor, even when rainfall is favorable.

Estimating the multivariate effects of six climatic variables on maize yield

The multivariate regression model was highly explanatory ($R^2 = 0.959$, $F = 24.1$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that climatic variables collectively account for almost all observed yield variation. Among the six variables, rainfall, air temperature, and soil temperature were statistically significant predictors. Rainfall exerted a modest but positive effect, highlighting its necessity for crop establishment, but its

limited coefficient implies that distribution matters more than totals. Temperature ($\beta = -0.355$, $p < 0.01$) emerged as the strongest negative predictor, followed closely by soil temperature ($\beta = -0.312$, $p < 0.05$), confirming that thermal stress is the principal yield constraint.

By contrast, solar radiation, relative humidity, and wind speed were not statistically significant. Their effects may be indirect, shaping crop performance through interactions with rainfall and temperature rather than standalone influences. This finding echoes Sinclair & Muchow (1999), who argued that crop yields are most sensitive to the balance of available water (rainfall, soil moisture) and energy (radiation, heat), with excess thermal energy tipping systems into stress.

The climate–yield relationship in Ejule is primarily governed by compound thermal stress rather than water deficits alone, aligning with Lobell & Field (2007) who identified temperature rise as the most severe global threat to maize production.

Conclusion

This study assessed the long-term interactions between climate variability and maize production in Ejule, Ofu Local Government Area, Kogi State, Nigeria, over a 31-year period (1992–2023). The results reveal a climate profile defined by high rainfall variability and a consistent warming trend in both temperatures,

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

both of which exert profound impacts on maize productivity. Maize yield trends displayed three distinct phases stagnation during the 1990s and early 2000s, moderate gains in the 2010s, and a plateau since 2019 suggesting that although improvements in seeds and farming practices have offered temporary relief, yields are now constrained by thermal stress and erratic rainfall patterns.

The multivariate regression analysis confirmed that while rainfall remains an essential driver of maize establishment and growth, temperatures emerged as the most critical limiting factors, jointly explaining much of the observed yield variability. These findings underscore that future maize production in Ejule is more threatened by rising temperatures than by changes in rainfall amounts alone.

In terms of food security, the study concludes that smallholder farmers in Ejule are increasingly vulnerable to climate-induced risks. Unless deliberate adaptation strategies are implemented, yields are likely to stagnate or decline, undermining both household nutrition and income. Sustainable solutions must therefore integrate climate-smart practices that reduce exposure to rainfall variability, mitigate the effects of thermal stress, and strengthen the adaptive capacity of local farmers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are put forward to improve

maize productivity and strengthen resilience against climate variability in Ejule.

First, there is a need to establish localized climate monitoring systems to provide accurate and timely data on rainfall onset, cessation, and intra-seasonal distribution. Strengthening climate forecasting and early warning services through NIMET, with targeted dissemination to farmers via extension agents, radio, and mobile platforms, will ensure that farmers receive actionable information. Community-level weather observatories should also be encouraged to complement national datasets and deliver place-specific advisories directly to farming households.

Farmers should be supported through education programs that emphasize the link between climate variability and maize performance. Such programs will enable them to adjust planting dates and cropping calendars more effectively in response to changing rainfall patterns. Wider adoption of improved hybrid maize varieties that are tolerant to short and irregular growing seasons is also necessary, alongside stronger promotion of soil fertility management practices. These include the use of organic manures, crop rotation, and cover crops, which help replenish soil nutrients, improve structure, and counteract declining yields.

In addition, interventions should prioritize the management of temperature and soil heat stress, since these were found to be critical constraints

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

on maize production. Agronomic measures such as mulching, crop residue retention, and conservation tillage should be encouraged to reduce soil heat loads and conserve moisture. Complementary to these practices, small-scale irrigation and water-harvesting systems should be introduced to buffer against mid-season droughts and stabilize production when rainfall distribution is unreliable.

The distribution of heat- and drought-tolerant maize varieties developed by research institutes such as CIMMYT and IITA should be expanded to reach smallholder farmers in Ejule. At the

References

Adger, W. N. (2006). Vulnerability. *Global Environmental Change*, 16(3), 268–281.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2006.02.006>

Adejuwon, S. A. (2019). Rainfall seasonality in the Niger River Basin. *International Journal of Climatology*, 39(1), 25–38.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.5801>

Adeyeri, O. E., Laux, P., Lawin, A. E., & Kunstmann, H. (2019a). Analysis of climate extremes over Nigeria: Observations and reanalysis data. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 137(3), 2509–2524.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-018-2716-7>

same time, extension services need to be strengthened to deliver training in climate-smart agriculture practices, including water management, soil conservation, and crop diversification. Policy measures such as subsidized inputs, affordable credit, and crop insurance will further support farmers in adapting to climate risks. Encouraging the formation of farmer cooperatives will also improve access to resources, facilitate collective investment in adaptation technologies, and strengthen market opportunities.

Adeyeri, O. E., Laux, P., Lawin, A. E., & Kunstmann, H. (2019b). Climate change in West Africa: Past, present and future. *Climate Dynamics*, 52(3–4), 1995–2014.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-018-4230-6>

Ajetomobi, J. (2016). Climate change impacts on maize production in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 6(2), 45–59.

Ajetomobi, J., Abiodun, A., & Hassan, R. (2011). Economic impact of climate change on irrigated rice agriculture in Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 6(1), 1–15.

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

- Amejo, A. (2018). Effects of climate variability on crop production in the Guinea Savanna belt of Nigeria. *Journal of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development*, 10(5), 89–98.
- FAO. (2015). *World reference base for soil resources 2014, update 2015*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Hatfield, J. L., & Prueger, J. H. (2015). Temperature extremes: Effect on plant growth and development. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, 10, 4–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2015.08.001>
- IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the IPCC*. Cambridge University Press.
- Jalloh, A., Nelson, G. C., Thomas, T. S., Zougmore, R., & Roy-Macauley, H. (2013). *West African agriculture and climate change: A comprehensive analysis*. International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI).
- Keay, R. W. J. (1989). *Trees of Nigeria*. Oxford University Press.
- Lobell, D. B., & Field, C. B. (2007). Global scale climate–crop yield relationships and the impacts of recent warming. *Environmental Research Letters*, 2(1), 014002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/2/1/014002>
- Nicholson, S. E. (2013). The West African Sahel: A review of recent studies on rainfall variability and trends. *ISRN Meteorology*, 2013, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/453521>
- NBS. (2022). *Nigeria Gross Domestic Product Report (Q4 2021)*. National Bureau of Statistics, Abuja.
- Odekunle, T. O. (2004). Rainfall and the length of the growing season in Nigeria. *International Journal of Climatology*, 24(4), 467–479. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.1012>
- Olaniyan, A. B. (2015). Maize: Panacea for hunger in Nigeria. *African Journal of Plant Science*, 9(3), 155–174.
- Ozor, N., & Nnaji, C. (2020). Climate change and the uncertainties facing agriculture in Nigeria. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 15(4), 555–565.

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu

Irish International Journal of Engineering and Scientific Studies

I. Int. J. Eng. Sci. S.

Volume: 8; Issue: 05,

September-October, 2025

ISSN: 2853-4387

Impact Factor: 7.96

Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/ijess>

- Schlenker, W., & Roberts, M. J. (2009). Nonlinear temperature effects indicate severe damages to U.S. crop yields under climate change. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 106(37), 15594–15598. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0906865106>
- Seneviratne, S. I., Nicholls, N., Easterling, D., Goodess, C. M., Kanae, S., Kossin, J., & Zhang, X. (2012). Changes in climate extremes and their impacts on the natural physical environment. In: *Managing the risks of extreme events and disasters to advance climate change adaptation* (pp. 109–230). Cambridge University Press.
- Shiferaw, B., Prasanna, B. M., Hellin, J., & Bänziger, M. (2011). Crops that feed the world 6: Past successes and future challenges to the role played by maize in global food security. *Food Security*, 3(3), 307–327. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-011-0140-5>
- Sinclair, T. R., & Muchow, R. C. (1999). Radiation use efficiency. *Advances in Agronomy*, 65, 215–265. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113\(08\)60914-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2113(08)60914-1)
- Sultan, B., & Gaetani, M. (2016). Agriculture in West Africa in the twenty-first century: Climate change and impacts scenarios, and potential for adaptation. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 7, 1262. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.01262>
- Tesfaye, K., Gbegbelegbe, S., Cairns, J. E., Shiferaw, B., Prasanna, B. M., Sonder, K., & Robertson, R. (2015). Maize systems under climate change in sub-Saharan Africa: Potential impacts on production and food security. *International Journal of Climate Change Strategies and Management*, 7(3), 247–271. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCCSM-01-2014-0005>

Iwu Elias Odinaka, Prof. J.c. Ajadike and Prof. S. Okonkwo Ogbu